

DIFFICULTIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

This thesis describes the problems of students studying in the medical field, various methods of solving problems in English. It includes reflections and research results, various difficulties in teaching a foreign language, and actions and measures aimed at improving students' knowledge.

English is an important language in medicine today. Many scientific articles, textbooks, and international conferences are written in English. Therefore, learning English is essential for medical professionals. However, there are various challenges to this process. First, medical terminology is very complex and unique. Many medical terms are derived from Latin and Greek, making it difficult to remember and pronounce them correctly. For example, learning words like "gastroenterology" or "otolaryngology" takes time and patience. Second, medical texts are complex and difficult to understand and translate. In particular, scientific articles and clinical research reports are written in highly academic language and specialized terminology, which can be a major obstacle for new learners. Third, developing English communication skills in practical training can also be problematic. Medical students and professionals may struggle with the inability to speak English fluently when interacting with patients, colleagues, or participating in international conferences. To overcome these difficulties, it is recommended to attend special medical English courses, use a medical glossary, and regularly read scientific articles. It may also be useful to watch medical podcasts and video lessons.

A distinctive feature of teaching English in medicine is a special approach to teaching this subject. In secondary vocational education institutions, a foreign language is one of the general education subjects and an important component of the training of future specialists. In the secondary vocational education system. The subject "Foreign Language" plays an important role in education, in the process of studying it, students develop their skills and abilities. English is a means of communication, for example, English plays a major role in obtaining information from the Internet. According to the educational standard, the basics of English grammar and phonetics play an important role in teaching students in English classes. Teaching English in medicine is built on the main clear goal: communicative actions are built on the basis of professional conditions, goals, taking into account professional attention, and

thus the introduction of professional skills into the educational process is achieved. However, despite the awareness of the need for knowledge and the need for future specialists to fully understand the potential of fluent knowledge of a foreign language and its importance, medical students studying English usually do not pay enough attention to learning it and are not very competent in this regard. The process of learning English is not simple, it requires a lot of time and effort, so there are a number of difficulties, and each student has his own reason. For example: - monotonous and monotonous teaching methods; - as a result, the complexity of the level of teaching English leads to a lack of interest in lessons; - difficulties in perceiving and memorizing a large text, material and lexical material; - lack of ability to learn English; - low level of knowledge acquired in the process of learning a foreign language or lack of a basic level; - language barrier, inability to express one's opinion, fear of making mistakes;

Not knowing how to use English in real life. Therefore, one of the main tasks of every teacher is to overcome all these difficulties by creating psychological and pedagogical conditions for the English language, to arouse great interest and desire in learning English in doctors. One of the most important aspects is to help students understand what important role English will play in their future lives, giving examples from life and showing its relevance to their profession. The teacher must help each student, that is, to increase self-confidence, to arouse interest in learning the language in students, and to use various methods to master it. Future medical workers should be able to use foreign literature to obtain information relevant to their field from the Internet. Computers are widely used by medical workers. Special and primary attention is paid to working with instructions for the use of medicines, which means that a medical student, using his knowledge gained from English, can correctly express his opinion in English when obtaining new information, how to use a new medicine, and solving a problem. To overcome these difficulties, it is necessary to use active methods, and to provide doctors with the right motivation for independent mastery of English.

It is necessary to ensure that students graduating from medical institutions can continue their studies in the magistracy or improve their skills abroad and gain experience. Various methods and techniques can be used in the process of teaching English. For example, holding various games, organizing competitions and involving students in English Olympiads. In addition, we should encourage students to acquire knowledge independently. Medical workers should often communicate in English to improve their knowledge and experience, for example, they should meet with friends or a foreigner on the Internet and communicate with him only in English.

So, English plays an important role in medicine and they are inextricably linked. Every student learning English should use all opportunities to overcome these difficulties and work more on himself.

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